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EMPOWERING STUDENTS: THE ROLE OF CAMPUS RADIO IN FIGHTING SOCIAL VICES

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Abstract: Flooding is a natural disaster that occurs when an excessive amount of water overflows from its natural source, such as rivers, lakes, or oceans, submerging land that is usually dry. This phenomenon typically results from heavy or prolonged rainfall, which causes the water levels in rivers or other water bodies to rise beyond their normal limits. As a consequence, the excess water escapes its natural boundaries, inundating surrounding land areas. In urban environments, flooding may also occur when drainage systems become overwhelmed during torrential rainfall, leading to water spilling into streets and nearby homes. Flooding can cause significant damage to properties, disrupt livelihoods, and pose severe risks to public health and safety. Understanding the causes and impacts of flooding is critical for effective disaster management, as well as for implementing preventive and adaptive strategies to mitigate its effects. This paper examines the causes, consequences, and possible solutions to flooding, with a focus on both natural and man-made factors contributing to this pervasive environmental challenge.

Keywords: Flooding, Natural Disaster, Rainfall, Overflow, Drainage System

INTRODUCTION

Social vices have existed for a very long time, primarily when a society's ideals and actual accomplishments diverge significantly. Elujekwute (2019) defines social vices as indisciplined behaviours as well as situations that go against social norms and ideals. In any case, some societal situations are harmful. These circumstances hinder a society's members from reaching their greatest potential. Cultism, kidnapping, rape, ritual killing, drug sales, armed robbery, and misconduct in exams are examples of social vices.

When the National Association of Adventurers (Supreme Vikings Confraternity) began operating at UNIPORT in 1982, social vices began to appear at the University of Port Harcourt. Later, the Klansmen fraternity created the Deebam group while the Supreme Vikings gave birth to another cult organisation called Dewell. Both groups fought for dominance and caused trouble even outside of educational settings (Birabil and Okanezi, 2017).

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In today's Nigerian universities, social vices are common. The quantity of social vices that are frequently observed on campus makes this clear. There would seldom be a day that passed without some sort of criminal behaviour documented. It is clear that social vices are a major issue for everyone in our society. There isn't a single higher education institution in Nigeria that hasn't dealt with the threat of social vices at some point because it is the most significant issue facing tertiary schools there. The decisions that students make are greatly influenced by social forces. Students are likely to succumb to social pressure in an atmosphere where social vices are prevalent. At this stage, the mass media—radio in particular—have a significant role to play in reducing the threat of social vices. This is due to the media's gradual integration into our daily lives as informational, educational, advocacy, and entertainment sources. Folarin (2005, p.74) cites Lasswell (1948) as saying that the media serves three purposes: Correlation of the various elements of the environment (editorial function), transmission of the cultural heritage from one generation to the next (cultural transmission function), and environmental surveillance (news function).

The ability of the media to reach a broad audience through mass communication and make an impact wherever it can reach—which is now far and wide—makes it the most significant tool of society in the modern day. The media's reputation as the fourth estate of the realm is surely due to its capacity to establish agendas on a wide range of societal concerns. This is due to the fact that the media is the most ubiquitous and potent force for social change.

By emphasising the repercussions and impacts social vices have on society, the mass media, which has the potential to be a potent change agent, can significantly contribute to the reduction of social vices in higher education institutions. For pupils to be educated about the negative effects of social vices, media advocacy and communication are crucial. Students will be more exposed to the phenomena of social vices and given advice to refrain from indulging in them through the use of the media, particularly the radio, as a platform. It is important to make excellent use of the media's strong and constructive role in the global fight and advocacy against social vices.

Essentially, this study evaluated how well campus radio programs worked to discourage social vices among college students.

Statement of the Problem

Campuses are not exempt from the negative effects of social vices because of the underlying issues they cause, which include the unsafe and unpredictable environment they foster wherever they are practiced. Campus social vices are planned in a nefarious and vicious way, leaving a path of devastation and harm in their wake. The status of homicides on campuses in recent years, where many lives have been taken, is the most upsetting issue. The phenomenon of social vices on our campuses has persisted despite efforts by the various branches of government and school administrators to curb the undesirable trend of social vices.

As a result, the terrible effects of social vices have played a significant role in the expulsion of some students, the suspension of many others, and the frustration of others. In summary, social vices are now a problem for the government as a whole, not just parents and educators. The fact that social vices, particularly cultism and exam malpractice, are discouraged worldwide is worth mentioning. Since young people hold the key to our nation's

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future and cultism and exam cheating are on the rise in educational institutions, the entire cornerstone of our progress as a nation is at risk. As such, young people are the easy victims of these crimes.

Given the amount of influence they have over their listeners, radio stations—campus radio in particular—have a significant role to play in reducing the social vices that students in higher education commit. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effects of campus radio programs in the effort to combat social vices among undergraduates.

Research Questions

1. In what ways do campus radio programmes influence students in a bid to curb social vices in tertiary institutions?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of campus radio programmes in curbing social vices among students in tertiary institutions?
3. What are the challenges associated with the use of campus radio for curbing social vices on campus?

Theoretical Framework

The Agenda Setting Theory serves as the theoretical foundation for our investigation. According to this theory, which emerged from Maxwell McComb and Donald Shaw's research in 1999, the media sets the agenda for public discourse because of their focus on a specific topic. "The press is significantly more than a purveyor of information and opinion.... It may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think about, but it is stunningly successful much of the time in telling its readers what to think about," Cohen (1963, p. 1–3) commented in his explanation.

The argument's content further makes it possible to understand the priming and framing concepts. Priming is the theory that "the media draw attention to some aspects of political life at the expense of others" in agenda setting and, implicitly, opinion formation (Baran & Davis 2012, p. 348). Even though framing and priming are related, framing makes the assumption that minor alterations in the way a situation is described could influence the way that media viewers perceive it.

Therefore, agenda-setting is relevant to this job since the media is in charge of raising awareness and supporting the effort to stop students in higher education institutions from engaging in social vices. It will establish the goal for members of society to refrain from engaging in any kind of social vices.

The Concept of Broadcast Programme

Content created and packaged for public consumption and distribution is known as broadcast programming. Providing programming that will appeal to a certain audience segment is the station's or networks main duty. A station's success will depend on its capacity to reach the target demographic. Its programming strategy and mission are essential to its survival. Programming is therefore radio's most visible and essential product. A broadcast station depends on its programs to keep its listeners interested. Programs are the station's content. The broadcast station won't survive without programming. The station survives and gains prominence thanks to its broadcast programming.

Causes of Social Vices

Igwe (2014) defines social vices as anti-social behaviours that violate social norms, values, and more. These behaviours include, but are not limited to, rape, financial fraud, impersonation, cultism, rape, smoking, hooliganism, gambling, profanity, sexual harassment, rape, and cultism. Regretfully, these days, the majority of

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these vices are prevalent on campuses. An institution, state, or nation that is free of social vices is uncommon because social vices are so common in society.

Anasi (2010, pp. 2-4) states that a number of factors contribute to social vices, some of which include:

Peer Pressure: One of the main causes of social vices is peer pressure. Young people spend more time at home or at school with their pals. They are easily swayed because of their frail character and young age. Young people are highly curious and want to learn, have fun, and do new things, which leads them to smoke, drink, engage in sexual activity, and so forth.

Parental negligence: the majority of young people who participate in social vices come from dysfunctional households. A youth may indulge in social vices if they do not receive the care, supervision, and attention they need from their parents. These traps primarily affect children whose parents are permissive and uninvolved. They move with the wrong people, no one asks them where they go, and no one monitors their academic progress. The ability to do whatever without parental scrutiny has a detrimental impact on young people.

Unemployment: According to experts, Nigeria's young unemployment rate is twice as high as the country's official estimate. According to Zakaria (2006), young people in African nations are more susceptible to the manipulations of agent's provocateurs due to the rising rate of unemployment and their dread of a dismal future. These include resentful politicians, religious propagandists, and avaricious multinational corporations that use these young people to further their own agendas. Zakaria is adamant that youth restlessness in developing nations is caused by a lack of employment options, which can have fatal results.

Inadequate Educational Opportunities and Resources: Cohesion, grandeur, and national prestige are all directly impacted by high-quality education. The degree of patriotism and contribution to national integration and advancement of young people is determined in part by the knowledge and skills they gain. The result of young people not attending school is that hundreds of them wander the streets of Nigerian cities. There are no chances for postsecondary education for those who succeed in finishing high school. They are disoriented and easily accessible for antisocial behaviour because they were not given the opportunity to fulfil their full potential (Onyekpe, 2007).

Lack of Basic Infrastructure: In Nigeria, the majority of urban slums and rural villages lack access to industry, commercial facilities, electricity, drinkable water, health care, and communication. The need for a fair allocation of resources is the driving force behind social unrest in the nation.

Common Social Vices among Students' in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions

Cultism: According to Erika and Elda (2015), secret cults are organizations that spread strange secret doctrines that are only known to their members. Cults are frequently linked to occultism or the possession of mystical power. However, it is challenging to determine the validity of this reasoning due to their somewhat covert method of operation. Members of cults typically partake in gangster activities, such as using cocaine, marijuana (Indian hemp), and even human blood. They enjoy watching other people suffer and perish horribly.

Examination Malpractice: Any act of commission or omission that jeopardises the integrity and validity of a test is considered examination malpractice (Ministry of Education, Benue State, 2001). It is an act of disdain for all the guidelines that govern how to perform an examination or evaluation procedure properly. Exam misconduct has evolved in recent years from basic "giraffing," in which students occasionally stretch their necks to get a sight

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of what they wish to copy from other students' scripts, to a number of complex techniques. Some applicants write pertinent information about the course or subject on various items, body parts, or even clothing, which they then recopy during tests. While some students exchange question papers with their answers written on them during an exam, others smuggle in lecture notes from which they copy. Some students even employ more talented people to write their exams for them.

Drug Abuse: Despite what some people mistakenly think, drugs are more than only compounds that change mood, perception, or normal awareness. They also include what are often referred to as medicine. Substance abuse is defined as the use of any substance, particularly self-administration, in a way that is not consistent with a culture's accepted medical or social norms (Elujekwute, Danburam, Zakariah, and James, 2021). It's important to note that while using opioid analgesics prescribed by a doctor to relieve pain is perfectly acceptable, self-administration of the same medication in the same amounts to relieve stress or sadness or to create euphoria is regarded as egregious misuse.

Sexual Promiscuity: Another major sin that should raise serious concerns is sexual promiscuity among Nigerian university students. After experiencing freedom for the first time, some students get so enamoured with illicit lovemaking that they devote most of their time and energy to it, even at the expense of their academic performance. Others stop attending lectures entirely in order to attend dates with boyfriends or "sugar daddies." Sexual promiscuity may result in unintended pregnancies, premature births, or even death. Even worse is the fact that some students have become so morally blind that they just depend on their sexuality to "pass" their exams.

Obscene Dressing: In Nigeria, tertiary educational institutions have been plagued with obscene attire, especially from female students. The majority of ladies take off their clothes, show off their boobs and navels, and wear minis that barely cover their bottoms to show off their huge cleavages. Nowadays, it seems like wearing sleeveless or see-through tops without a bra and becoming partly nude are necessary for being stylish. As a result, both students and lecturers suffer greatly from this sensual attire since it makes it difficult for them to focus on their academic work.

Resultant Effects of Social Vices among Students

Even if the saying "young people are tomorrow's leaders" is still true, there are real concerns that many of them might not be able to assume their proper roles in society given the present events in the nation. Due to peer pressure and the carelessness of parents and the government, some of them in Nigeria have turned to social vices, ruining the lives of numerous people throughout the nation. According to Bhatti (2009, p. 75), one of the main consequences of social difficulties is that "our harmony is disturbed and in its place in the society there is hostility and suspicion." These also cause agony and misery and widespread social discontent.

A high prevalence of social vices can damage a nation's and a family's reputation. It can upset a household's equilibrium and cause instability. The great prevalence of social vices in a nation detracts from its reputation. Such nations are despised by other nations as being weak, corrupt, and lethal. They occasionally forbid immigration to their nations, and even when they do, stringent screening procedures are implemented. Foreign and domestic investors will be reluctant to put money into a corrupt nation. As a result, there will be fewer businesses and industries that could have employed people, which will raise the unemployment rate and impede the growth and development of the country:

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These days, social problems follow a revolving-door policy, claims Iranin (2009). One disappears, and another appears. One tournament after another, people are battling for the top spot. As a result, the drive to succeed could lead to new social maladies, which make it difficult for people to coexist peacefully in a community. Although there are numerous social issues that affect teens, adults can also experience them, such as criminal breaches of trust, corruption, marital infidelity, gambling, theft, etc.

Effectiveness of Campus Radio Programmes in Curbing Social Vices in Nigeria

It has been argued that the mass media play a critical role in achieving societal goals, whether they are related to social, health, infrastructure, politics, education, or security development. One of the most significant socialization institutions and, in actuality, the main cultural sector in charge of disseminating ideas in Nigerian society is the mass media (Pate, 2011). By carrying out their own distinct societal tasks, other socialization institutions like the church, family, schools, political organizations, etc., essentially reinforce the mass media. This demonstrates how the influence of the media on society may shape prevailing attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions. Thus, how might the mass media's dominant role in society—particularly the radio—be used to mobilize people against social vices in Nigeria?

The foundation of mobilization against acts of insecurity is the radio's correlation and surveillance capabilities. According to the surveillance role, radio as a medium must inform the public in order to influence opinions and adopt attitudes. According to the correlation role, the radio should connect news and other social events to people's lives and surroundings. This is accomplished by interpreting and elucidating the effects of events on the environment and way of life of the general public, particularly the effects of actions that encourage social vices in the community. It is anticipated that society will eventually turn against such activities with the use of effective information.

There are numerous radio programs aimed at raising awareness of social vices and discouraging their occurrence. These crime-specific programs, like Police Diary on Radio Nigeria and Eagle on Radio Nigeria, which are sponsored by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), and Crux of the Matter Crime Watch and other programs on campus radio stations, educate the public about social vices. Among the efforts made by radio to use publicity to educate the public about acts that encourage social vices are the various jingles and promotional messages against violence that are frequently played on the majority of radio stations. In order to make society uncomfortable and prevent such acts from flourishing, awareness-raising is crucial.

It is crucial to prioritise reporting on social vices for the public's benefit. Due to reporting that is largely focused on expanding audience size and profit, the media has been accused of contributing to the worsening of crime in Nigeria. Following an analysis of radio coverage of social vices, Pate (2011) identified common practices that radio stations adopt that tend to contribute negatively to social vices. These practices include: selectively reporting prejudicial stereotypes about groups and individuals; reporting intergroup conflicts outside of their fundamental sociological, economic, political, and other contexts; providing shallow and episodic coverage; completely blacking out certain groups, individuals, or communities; using sensational, misleading, and inflammatory headlines to increase sales; publishing inflammatory statements against certain individuals or groups as letters to the editor; attributing statements made by individuals to groups without supporting facts; and more. Radio stations

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must stop doing these things if they want to have a significant influence on the fight against social vices in Nigeria; otherwise, the mass media would be perceived as encouraging social vices.

Reports on human trafficking, kidnapping, and other social vices that can lead to insecurity must be given special airtime and space by radio stations. This serves to highlight the detrimental effects that such actions have on society. Among the recommendations made by journalists in a study on how to fight terrorism through mass media strategies was the allocation of specific airtime and space for reporting social vices, as well as the sponsorship of reporters to conduct independent investigations of acts of social vices in the nation (Udoudo and Diriyai, 2012). This will give the necessary support for the detrimental effects that these crimes have on society. "Get all these things (acts of social vices and other acts of insecurity) out in the open, describe them, ridicule them in the press, and sooner or later, public opinion will sweep them away," as Pulitzer, cited in Oloyede 2011, p. 64, notes. This might be a slow yet efficient procedure.

Ordinary people ought to use radio stations to expose criminal activity and raise public awareness of social vices. Four University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT) students were brutally murdered in Aluu, a town in Rivers State, Nigeria, in 2012. This incident demonstrated the importance of citizen journalism in addressing social injustices. After the video of the four lads clubbing and being burned alive was posted online, the story quickly gained widespread attention. The tale was subsequently disseminated by radio stations, particularly from the perspective of the public outcry sparked by the murder that was recorded. Media professionals must be dedicated to the different ways that the mass media can be used to effectively combat societal vices, as explained below. In this sense, the public and members of the mainstream media should work together in complementary roles.

Analysis of Radio Uniport Programmes Vis sa Vis their Campaign against Social Vices Radio Uniport named Unique 88.5fm programme schedule runs from Sunday to Saturday and starts at 6:00am to 10:10pm. The programme line-up of Unique FM is structured in a manner that aims at attracting and sustaining the interest of their audience. This means that the station has a variety of programmes aimed at educating, informing and entertaining the audience. However, in relation to this study the station has only few programmes that addresses the issue of social vices amongst students, among such programmes are Zoe Elizir, a programme that runs for an hour and with the objective of encouraging young people to be strong and conduct their activities in a way that will be worthy of emulation by others.

Hug is another of such programme an acronym that means Help Us Grow, it runs for 45 minutes and offers wise counsel to the audience, the counsel is offered in a manner that touches all aspect of the audience life, hence, the importance of the programme is that the audience feel that they are not alone and that there is a programme that can contribute to their positive and all round growth.

Another programme is Our Student, a 30 minutes programme that gives the students the opportunity and platform to be heard not just by the stations personnel but also by the school authority, the programme gives the students the chance to air their grievances on whatever issues that borders them of which acts of social vices are not left out. The significance of this programme rests on the fact that it gives the students the feel that they matter to the school authority.

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Counsel to the students is an hour programmes that treats issues of dating and the audience can handle it. This programme is vital to the campaign against social vices as it offers wise counsel to students on how best to handle issues of the opposite sex and helps them avoid engaging in any form of rape.

Flava is another of such programmes, a BBC world serve trust with 30 minutes airtime that targets young people and treats a variety of issues that affects them. This programme is very crucial to the campaign against social vices as it discusses different kinds of social vices perpetrated among students, their resultant effects and the measures that can be adopted to curb the vices. The programme also interviews professionals who shed more light on the topic at hand and offers professional advice to the audience.

Point counter-point is an hour programme that aims at engaging the students in intellectual debates on issues that borders on student life on campus. The programme not only adds to the intellectual growth of the debators but also to the listeners. Crux of the matter is 55 minutes programme dedicated to identifying social vices and proffering solutions to the vices. This programme directly focuses and treats issues of social vices, the programme, sometimes, hosts masters students as guests' speakers. This is due to the level of experience they have on issues that borders on students and social vices. The programme is very significant to the campaign against social vices as it not only identifies the social vices perpetrated among students but it also offers possible solutions to help curb and eliminate students engagement in social vices.

Motivational talks is a 30 minutes programme that offers positive motivation to the students, the programme encourages students to be upright in their dealings and shun every act that will showcase them in a negative light. Crime watch, a 20 minutes surveillance programme on crime that identifies crime incidents and proffers possible measures that can be used to avoid the perpetration of crimes in the future. Finally, Lifeline with Aunty ID is a campus radio programme that contributes to the campaign against social vices among students, as it is an interactive programme that offers wise counsel on relationships, sex and dating it serves as a right guidance for the students to handle dating with the opposite sex.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprises of 400 level undergraduate students of University of Port Harcourt, which is 2021/2022 session, which according to the records department is put at 8205. The National Statistical Service of Australia sample size calculator was used to determine a sample size of 273 for this study. The multistage sampling technique was used in this study..

RESULTS

Findings from the study indicated that 83% of the population overwhelmingly agreed that campus radio programmes can help to influence students positively which will help in curbing the practice of social vices in tertiary institutions. Also, a cross section of the respondents indicated that in a bid to curb social vices in tertiary institutions, campus radio programmes influences students in various ways by promoting positive behavior, increasing student's awareness level on dangers of social vices, encouraged students to engage in dialogue and be open about issues related to social vices on and off campus.

The study also gathered from 79% of the respondents that campus radio programmes are quite effective in curbing social vices among students in tertiary institutions. 75% of them explained that the effectiveness of radio programmes has been felt in the following ways; it improved students orientation about social vices, it proffered

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adequate measures to curbing the rise of social vices, it reduced the rate at which social vices are perpetrated, it advised school authority on proactive measures to adopt in order to avoid students engagement in social vices.

In an interview with presenters and staff of Radio Uniport named Unique 88.5fm, the following were gathered as the challenges affecting the radio station from effectively contributing to curbing social vices in the institution; These challenges span from lack of funding for the station, lack of station independence, unavailability of trained and experienced personnel, poorly paid staff, inadequate incentive for staff, commercialization of media content for profit purposes, etc.

Discussion

The study's first objective was to examine the ways campus radio programmes influence students in a bid to curb social vices in tertiary institutions and it was revealed that campus radio programmes can positively influence students' behaviour which can help to reduce the practice of social vices in tertiary institutions. Findings showed that Unique 88.5fm has been playing its role through its programming in influencing students in a bid to curb social vices in tertiary institutions. Campus radio programs can influence students by promoting positive messages and values, which can help in curbing social vices. By broadcasting pro-social content, such as promoting community service, volunteerism, and responsible behavior, radio stations can instill positive values in students. This result is consistent with Pate's (2011) assertion that the mass media is one of the most significant socialization institutions and, in fact, the main cultural sector in charge of disseminating ideas in Nigerian society. Students can express their thoughts and experiences by participating in interactive conversations, debates, and interviews on campus radio shows. Such platforms facilitate open dialogue on social issues and create a sense of community, encouraging students to address social vices collectively.

Through the second objective, the study sought to examine the level of effectiveness of campus radio programmes in curbing social vices among students in tertiary institutions. The study found out that Unique 88.5fm radio programmes are quite effective in contributing to curbing social vices among students in tertiary institutions. The study revealed that the effectiveness of radio programmes has been felt in the following ways; it improved students orientation about social vices, it proffered adequate measures to curbing the rise of social vices, it reduced the rate at which social vices are perpetrated, it advised school authority on proactive measures to adopt in order to avoid students engagement in social vices. Campus radio programs through its educational content on various social issues like substance abuse, examination malpractice, sexual harassment, and mental health, has raised awareness among students. This knowledge has empowered students to make informed decisions and resist negative peer pressure. Through the launch of campaigns and initiatives focused on raising awareness and promoting behavioral change. For example, running campaigns against bullying, malpractice, discrimination, or substance abuse has helped to influence students' attitudes and behaviors positively, contributing to a safer and healthier campus environment. Radio personalities and guests on campus radio can serve as role models for students by sharing personal stories of overcoming challenges or advocating for positive change. These role models can inspire students to emulate their behavior and become agents of change within the campus community. Also, Radio personalities and guests on campus radio has served as role models for students by sharing personal stories of overcoming challenges or advocating for positive change. These role models have over time inspired students to emulate their behavior and become agents of change within the campus community.

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In the third objective of investigating the challenges associated with the use of campus radio for curbing social vices on campus. Lack of station autonomy, a shortage of skilled and experienced workers, low employee compensation, a lack of incentives for employees, and the commercialization of media material for financial gain were among the issues noted. However, Pate (2011) outlined common practices that radio stations use that tend to hinder their ability to effectively contribute to curbing social vices. These practices include: publishing inflammatory statements against certain people or groups as letters to the editor; attributing statements made by individuals to groups that are not supported by facts; reporting intergroup conflicts outside of their fundamental sociological, economic, political, and other contexts; providing shallow and episodic coverage; completely blacking out certain groups, individuals, or communities; using inflammatory, misleading, and sensational headlines to increase sales; publishing inflammatory statements against certain people or groups as letters to the editor; publishing inflammatory statements against certain people or groups.

Conclusion

This study examines how well campus radio works to combat social vices and how efforts to implement punitive measures to address modern campus evils are growing in tandem with the prevalence of social ills. Being a part of society at large, the university community is not exempt from the fight against the rise of social vices. Because media campaigns are raising public awareness of the law's position, the vast campaign against the wave is having an impact. No disrespect or lack of faith in Nigeria's educational system was intended by this study, nor was it intended to diminish its worth. Instead, it has demonstrated the necessity of morally sound viewpoints and value-added education for all parties involved in the education sector.

Recommendations

Based on the findings made in this study, the following recommendations were proffered;

1. It is imperative that parents and educators act as good and exemplary behavioural role models. It is widely accepted that a child's home is their first school. As such, parents have the greatest stake in this, as they must thoroughly supervise their children's socialisation and upbringing through careful observation, one-on-one moral counselling, and enviable parentage (Kayode, 2015, p. 21).
2. In order to eradicate the epidemic of social vices among undergraduates, campus radio stations should devote greater airtime to programs that directly threaten social vice issues. Additionally, higher education institutions ought to set up and improve their guidance and counselling departments in order to be more proactive in providing staff and students with the many types of formative counselling services.
3. The general media should also contribute to curbing social vices in the society. Institutional campuses must therefore implement more print and electronic media campaigns to raise awareness of the importance of avoiding social vices.

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